
Assessment of Surface Water Quality of Selected Rivers in Central Plateau, Jos – Nigeria for Off-Stream Uses

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ABSTRACT

The Central Zone of Plateau State is predominantly an agricultural settlement with the inhabitants involved in both dry and rainy season agriculture. The production of crops and rearing of animals are common in this part of the Plateau. Because of this, a lot of chemical fertilizer, organic manure and other agrochemicals are used in nourishing the farmlands. The area gets its water supply for drinking and other domestic uses from rivers, wells and a few boreholes. The predominant source is water gotten from rivers. Five of the numerous rivers were selected using purposive sampling for the study. Water samples were taken from each of the rivers and tested for selected water quality parameters. It was discovered that the water quality of all the rivers studied do not meet the World Health Organization (WHO) and the Nigeria Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) standards especially as sources of drinking water but could be exploited in irrigation agriculture and other off-stream uses like washing of household utensils. Suggestions were made for alternative sources of drinking water to prevent exposure to enteric disease-causing pathogens because of the high coliform bacterial counts.

INTRODUCTION

Nigeria is blessed with abundant surface water sources including the Central Zone of Plateau State. Water has been used by man for drinking, washing of household utensils, transportation, irrigation, hydro-electric power generation, recreation, fishing and industrial uses over the years. Despite all these important functions performed by water, its purity has over the millennia been affected negatively by human activities and industrialisation, making the search for clean water sources a burden on individuals, private organisations and the government. Human activities like farming, livestock production, mining and open defecation etc have added to the quality of organic and inorganic matter that enters water bodies especially surface water resulting in an increase in the chemical and microbial population of surface water.

Man has played an active role in surface water pollution, though other factors as pointed out by (Tebbut, 1992) who said "it is important to appreciate that all natural waters contain a variety of contaminants arising from erosion, leaching and weathering processes. Andrea (2018) did a similar study on water pollution and water quality assessment of major transboundary rivers from Banat (Romania),

which pointed to the need to protect our rivers from pollutants. The Nigerian Standard for Drinking Water Quality (NSDWQ) is the legally recognised and accepted standard for drinking water quality in Nigeria. NSDWQ sets mandatory limits concerning the constituents and contaminants of water that are hazardous to health or make water unfit for human use and suggests procedures and practices to ensure good practices or compliance to the mandatory limits. Water quality being a health-related issue, the Federal Ministry of Health with the Standard Organisation of Nigeria (SON) and with SON as the main organisation concern with the development of the National Standards in Nigeria are working with other relevant sectors to develop the NSDWQ. The health of a community depends to a large measure on the ample provision of a wholesome water supply. This wholesomeness of water according to (Rodda, 1976) can be assessed by using the below:

- i) **Aesthetic** – reasonably free from colour, turbidity, taste and odour.
- ii) **Toxicity** – chemically free from injurious substances like acids, alkalis and other poisons also not too saline or unduly hard and limit on radioactivity and
- iii) **Microbiological** – so low in pathogen content as not to present a risk to the health of consumers. This is usually assessed indirectly in terms of the content of faecal bacterial like coliform, *Escherichia coli*, *faecal streptococci* etc.

Miller (1994) sees water pollution as being connected with air pollution, land use practices and the number of people, farms and industries producing sewage. As suggested above by (Miller, 1994) the study area would be affected through land use practices, human population and the intricate connection that exists between air and water pollution. Anything that makes water to deviate from any of the below standards proposed by (Chinnock, 1998) is seen as polluted water or water not safe for human consumption and further said that water for human consumption should:

- (i) Be free from microbiological contamination
- (ii) Not have chemical concentrations greater than prescribed limits
- (iii) Be available in sufficient quantities to enable adequate domestic hygiene and
- (iv) Meet local standards for taste, odour and appearance.

Miller (1994) cited Rev. Jesse Jackson as saying that “we found our house, the planet with drinkable water, good soil to grow food and with clean air to breath. We must at least leave it in good shape as we found it, if not better”. This is a call for sustainability. Rivers and streams are being used in villages and urban centres as vehicle for transporting unwanted materials away from settlements or houses. This practice further pollutes the water making it unfit for human consumption, industrial uses as well as irrigation and recreational use. The great concern all over

the world today is the degradation of our much-cherished environment, while the critical problem of most societies today is that of producing an adequate and safe water supply for human consumption. Miller (1994) quoted the World Health Organisation (WHO) as saying that 1.5 billion people do not have a safe supply of drinking water and 1.7 billion lack adequate sanitation facilities. At least 5 million people die every year from water borne diseases that could be prevented by clean drinking water and better sanitation. Similar studies by (Eziashi, 1999 and Kwarfswang, 1999 and 2014) showed that most rivers on the Jos Plateau are highly polluted with the huge financial investment in water treatment and yet the high loss of human lives through water borne diseases, the pollution of water is better prevented than remedied.

The Study Area

The study area is within the Jos Plateau that is located at almost the centre of Nigeria geographical spread. It is located between latitude $80^{\circ} 24' N$ and longitude $80^{\circ} 32' S$ and $100^{\circ} 38' E$. Plateau State has an area of about 30,193² KM sharing boundaries with Nasarawa State on the South-West, Kaduna State to the North-West, Taraba State on the South-East and Bauchi State on the North East. Because of the high elevation (altitude) 1,200 metres to 1,892 metres above sea level, the State enjoys a cool and near temperate climate with average temperature ranging between 13°C and 22°C. The high altitude makes it the sources of many rivers that drained the state. It is rocky with plain lands in between the rock formations. A lot of inselbergs abound in the area and it is within the area that experienced a lot of volcanic activities in the past. The Central Plateau enjoys the same climatic conditions with the Northern Plateau. The Southern part of the Jos Plateau experiences a little variation in temperature and rainfall by being warmer and having a reduction in rainfall. The study area is made up of five Local Governments which includes Bokkos, Mangu, Pankshin, Kanke and Kanam. Irrigation is a source of livelihood of the inhabitants of the State. About 80% of the inhabitants in the selected villages of the Local Government Areas are farmers that practice both rainy and dry season farming alongside the rearing of animals (Kwarfswang, 1992, 2014).

Aims and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study is to establish the water quality status of the rivers water to enable the comparison of the water quality status of the selected rivers with the accepted limits of World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Federal Environmental Protection Agency Standards. The objectives of the study are to ascertain whether the selected rivers meet required standards for:

- (i) Drinking (the coliform bacterial counts) etc

- (ii) Washing of household utensils and laundry services (softness and hardness of the water)
- (iii) Irrigation (Turbidity and salinity).

The coliform bacteria count being used as an indicator organism was taken to represent the microbiological quality of the river waters since its presence in water implies the possibility of the presence of other microorganisms especially from faecal contamination or pollution, other physical and chemical properties were investigated to give a broader picture of the water quality from the investigated rivers.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Five of the numerous rivers that drain the study area were selected for the study; though with bias for those very close to human settlements and those that have water in their channels for a greater part of the year. A river was taken in each of the five Local Government Areas. The rivers are listed and coded below.

Table 1: Selected Rivers, Local Government Area and Code Names

Name of River	Local Government Area	Code Name
Rim	Mangu	R1
Jibam	Pankshin	R2
Met	Kanke	R3
Mabel	Bokkos	R4
Zai	Kanam	R5

Field Survey and Water sample collection.

Visits were made to the selected rivers to see the levels of human interaction and uses of the rivers. For each of the rivers, five water samples were taken at five different spots and the mean value was taken from the laboratory results. Sterile bottles and plastics containers were used for the water sample collection. A sterile bottle was tied to a long rod to collect the water samples. The collected water was immediately poured into a plastic container and taken to the laboratory for analysis same day of collection as suggested by (Hutton, 1983, Aneke, 1990, Keneth, 1993 and Miller, 1994).

Parameters Investigated

The below parameters were investigated.

a) Physical Parameters

- i) Total Dissolved solids
- ii) Suspended solids

} Turbidity

b) Chemical Parameters

- iii) PH

- iv) Chloride (Cl)
 - v) Calcium (Ca)
 - vi) Magnesium (Mg)
 - vii) Sulphate (SO₂⁴)
 - viii) Lead (Pb)
 - ix) Iron (Fe)
- } Water hardness and softness
- c) Microbiological
 - x) Coliform Counts (CC)

LABORATORY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results gotten after the laboratory analysis are presented in the tables below.

Table 2: Laboratory Values of Water Samples

Rivers	LABORATORY VALUES									
	Coliform Count (CC)	Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)	Suspended Solved (SS)	PH	CL	Ca	Mg	SO ₂ ⁴	Pb	Fe
R1	200	24	84	8.40	24	12	21	123	3.0	6.0
R2	180	28	74	8.30	37	12	26	104	3.0	23
R3	150	22	70	8.40	24	12	18	91	2.5	15
R4	138	26	58	8.40	24	16	13	102	1.5	20
R5	220	24	63	8.30	24	12	24	112	3.0	35

NB: All values are in milligram per litre except for PH

The aim of the research was to see if the rivers met the desired and acceptable water quality standards put forward by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA) of Nigeria. The results obtained from the laboratory analysis of the water samples in all the rivers shown values above the recommended WHO and FEPA standards of 0 colonies of coliform bacteria per 100mg/l of water; making all the rivers water unfit for human consumption or drinking. The same water bodies serve as drinking water for animals that drink directly from the river channel. The same water can as well be a source of infection for these animals since the high presence of the coliform bacteria can be used to assume the presence of other enteric disease-causing pathogens. Table 3 below shows the conformity or deviation of the laboratory values compared to the W.H.O standard which is also adopted by FEPA with little variation.

Table 3: Laboratory Values of Water Sample Compared to WHO/FEPA Limits

Rivers	LABORATORY VALUES									
	CC	TDS	SS	pH	Cl	Ca	SO ₄	Pb	Fe	Mg
R1	200	24	84	8.40	24	12	123	3.0	6.0	21
R2	180	28	74	8.30	37	12	104	3.0	23	26
R3	150	22	70	8.40	24	12	91	2.5	15	18
R4	138	26	58	8.40	24	16	102	1.5	20	13
R5	220	24	63	8.30	24	12	112	3.0	35	24
W.H.O/FEPA ACCEPTED LIMITS	0	1500	30	6.5-9.2	600	200	400	0.05	1	150

NB: All values are in milligram per litre except for pH.

Looking at table 2 above, all the rivers have coliform counts above 0 colonies of bacteria per 100 mg/l of water. All the rivers have water that is not fit for human use and other animals. The total dissolved solids are all very low compared to the W.H.O and FEPA standards but the suspended values are all above the accepted maximum permissive concentration levels in mg/l ranging from 58-84 mg/l. This high value can contribute to the turbidity of the water. The chloride, calcium, magnesium and sulphate values are below the WHO/FEPA desirable limits making the river water suitable for off-stream uses like drinking and other uses including irrigation and agriculture. Highly turbid water can affect plants' growth by affecting the stomata and lenticular openings on plants leaves and stems respectively. This will affect plants functions like photosynthesis and transpiration. The FEPA recommended pH limit for agriculture is 5.5 – 8.5 (Aina, 1996), making the water suitable for agricultural practices. The Lead (Pb) value in high ranging from a value of 1.5 – 3.0 mg/l against the limits given by WHO/FEPA of 0.05 mg/l. The Iron (Fe) values for all rivers is also high compared to the 1.0mg/l allowed by WHO/FEPA. The Lead (Pb) and Iron (Fe) values of the rivers is also high compared to the 1.0 mg/l allowed by WHO/FEPA. The Lead (Pb) and Iron (Fe) values of the sampled rivers water are above the recommended limits making them unsuitable and unfit for the desire uses.

SUGGESTIONS/RECOMMENDATIONS

The laboratory values of the water samples show their conformity or deviation from the accepted WHO/FEPA accepted limits and based on this, the following suggestions or recommendations are put forward.

1. There is the need for alternative water sources to be used as sources of drinking water and other domestic uses. Tube wells can be sunk and covered with

- movable lids, boreholes and if possible, the provision of treated potable water by individuals and government for the rural populace.
2. Educating the rural dwellers on the need for building toilets as against the open defecation in practice in the rural settlements. This will reduce the pollutant load entering the river channels during surface run-offs.
 3. Water of doubtful sources especially the one from the rivers should be boiled, filtered and chlorinated before drinking.

CONCLUSION

Though, the streams are not good sources of water for drinking and livestock watering, they could be fully utilized for irrigation agriculture. Proper education of the rural dwellers especially on the effects of open defecation on the sanitary standard of the ecosystem can help improve the stream water qualities.

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